

Types and Typology of Literary Concepts

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Abstract: Nowadays, several types of concepts are defined in the scientific literature, however there is no, A) the construction features of the relationship between different types of literal concepts, b) general established classification that allows us to determine how and in what way the operative units of thought interact.

Keywords: linguaculture, basic concept, thought, ethnolinguistic, mental unit.

There are different approaches to concept typology:

- 1) according to the degree of abstraction of the figurative component of the development of thought: from a specific picture to the one that forms the imagination expression, which generalizes a number of private images;
- 2) according to the interpretation of a concrete emotional image: the meaning of most words containing visual external features is explained using pictures in dictionaries: mental pictures, drafts, hyperonyms, frames, essayites, scenarios, kaleidoscopic concepts [Бабушкин 1996: 43-67];
- 3) according to the nature of translativity: the transition of the concept from one person to another and from one culture to the second culture in the process of communication. It should be noted, that translativity is considered the most important discursive property of concepts, since this property can be used to contradict concepts that are actively and passively turned, changed and not changed in content, translated and not included in other forms [Карасик 2003: 17-18];
- 4) according to the linguistic methods of expression (lexical and compositional-stylistic expositions, etc.)
- 5) by type of structure: one-level concepts, multi-level: conceptual, figurative, meaningful levels [Воркачев 2004: 7] and segment concepts;
- 6) by type of linguistic expression (nationwide, group, individual).

The list of types of concepts presented is not permanent, they are expanding with new structures of the imagination of knowledge. Concept typology allows us to show the diversity of the mental space of a literal concept.

Summarizing the above points, we believe that based on the basic principle of constructing a typology of concepts, they can be distinguished as follows:

- ✓ according to its semantic content: basic and cultural;
- ✓ according to the method used in speech: the moment is decreasing, emerging;

- ✓ according to the type of knowledge expression (cognitive) structure of the word: frames, scenes, scripts, etc.

According to its semantic content: *basic and cultural*.

Basic literal concepts. The main concepts are certain universal concepts that reflect the concepts of the spiritual life of society, formed in the socio-cultural space in certain historical periods [Талми 1999: 92]. The basic concepts are the universalia concepts (protoconcept) [Вежбицкая 1999: 53], manifested in scientific thought in the form of moral terms and logical operators, and in fiction as basic literal concepts.

The grammatical method of expressing basic concepts is central to the language system, and the grammatically formed concept occupies a central place in linguistic thought, with other means of expression standing around it.

There are basic concepts and specific cognitive units, represented by the archilexeme or identity of a particular lexico-semantic association, which require a generalization of structural, task and cognitive research methods.

Cultural literal concepts – considered a cognitive-semiological formation that occupies an intermediate place between linguistic signs and cognitive objects, lyrically form the mental capacity of our mind in speech, the ethno-cultural appearance of the universe [Алефиренко 2006: 151].

Any cultural expression (kulturema) is a specific concept, but not every specific concept can be a cultural expression. Cultural expression is understood as a group of specific signs of the linguistic landscape of the universe, reflecting the interaction of a set of signs of the cultural reserve of a particular people [Воробьев 1997: 44] and reality-object (sign) and reality-word (signifier). Through cultural expression, we understand the totality of three components: content, formal expression and reality-subject.

It should be mentioned, in linguistics, a concept outside the cognitive-communicative framework of a work is considered cultural, in which information of cultural significance is attached to the conceptual core.

Cultural concepts have, first of all, a mental essence that reflects the “spirit of the people”, which determines their anthropocentricity – orientation towards spirituality, subjectivity, sociability and “personal sphere” of the personality of ethnic thinking [Арутюнова 1991: 21-30; Воркачев 2003а: 5-12].

As an important category of linguistics, the cultural concept includes the following components:

1. value expression [Карасик, Слышкин 2001: 76], the basis of concept formation are objects of assessment of vital phenomena, in which the necessary things (physical and spiritual) for man and humanity are evaluated [Арутюнова 1999: 181];
2. has social value, because it is the composition of the valued image of the universe [Карасик 1996: 3], in which the element that evaluates as an axiological component in cultural concepts is not only present, but dominant;
3. emotional expression [Шаховский 1996: 80-96].

All of the above features of the cultural concept can be present in any literal concept.

Among the most important literal cultural concepts are dominants of value – the most fundamental meanings for a given culture, the totality of which constitutes a certain type of culture that is supported and maintained in the language. Yu.S. Stepanov calls them constants of culture [Степанов 1997]. The connection of the cultural concept with the values of society is due to the fact that a culture based on values is naturally reflected in and formed through an literal work.

The main concepts of culture: concepts of the spiritual sphere, assessments, natural states of person, which are the main categories of being that reflect the national image of the universe, are significant in that they are realized in the text in the form of literal cultural concepts. These concepts are the semantic and constructive core of the ethnolinguistic thought of any cultural space. They focus on the entire system of semantic representation of ethnic thought in the unity of paradigmatic, syntagmatic and linguacultural (value-meaningful) connections, as reflected in the literal text [Алефиренко 2006: 152].

Currently, a number of scientists also distinguish other types of linguistic literal concepts:

Linguistic literal – are subjective elements of culture expressed in language and speech. The main feature of the linguacultural expression, the sign of its difference in terms of logic and generalemiotic concepts, is in the specific way of the linguistic reality of the concept [Воркачев 2003б: 268; Григорьев 2003].

V.I. Karasik believes that the linguacultural concept is a conditional mental unit focused on the complex study of language, thought, and culture [Карасик 2001: 75-80]. The linguistic literal concept, on the other hand, is a unit of text aimed at the study of speech, thought and culture.

Hence, the linguacultural concept and the linguacultural literal concept consist of three structural structures: value, factual and figurative elements.

The factual element of the linguacultural concept is kept in verbal form in thought and can therefore be expressed directly in speech, while the figurative element can be defined in verbal form.

The linguacultural concept embodies the universal meaning, abstraction in the linguistic reality, the exact form of which is determined by the degree of abstraction, at the boundaries of which it is determined by the size of the lexico-semantic paradigm formed by units representing the concept in the language. It is established that the linguacultural literal concept is manifested in the text from the same point of view.

The linguacultural concept is multidimensional and consists of three levels: the first level is the system potential, that is, all the means by which the linguistic person of culture refers to the concept; the second level is the subject potential, that is, the arsenal of linguistic means stored in the consciousness of the individual. Within the third level, it is the only concept that exists in cultural and individual memory, divided into subjective concepts that function in separate genres and discourses [Слышкин 2004: 33-34].

The criterion for distinguishing linguacultural concepts, their belonging to the field of knowledge/thought that serves, provides a meaningful basis for moral, psychological, logical and religious terms that express spiritual values, which, of course, can be defined ethnoculturally both within the boundaries of one language and within the framework of the linguistic scientific paradigm – mindset.

Linguacultural literal concepts can be classified thematically in the same general as linguocognitive concepts:

- ✓ emotional [Красавский 2005: 38-43],
- ✓ expressive [Толочко 1999],
- ✓ textual [Слышкин 1999].

According to the principle of expression in literal speech, literal concepts are divided into the following types:

- ✓ individual,
- ✓ microgrouped,

- ✓ makrogrouped,
- ✓ national,
- ✓ civilisation,
- ✓ universal [Карасик 1996].

The linguacultural literal concept is polarized by its own mental nature from other units used in linguaculture (the science that studies the relationship between language and culture). Already, the interaction of language and culture is reflected precisely in thinking, since it is in the mind of the interaction of language and culture, therefore, any linguistic research is also considered a cognitive study at one time or another.

Concepts can also be differentiated according to the way they are used in speech:

- ✓ concepts that decreasing from being used in everyday life, such as “humility” [Карасик 2003: 18;
- ✓ developing concepts of the forming word, such as “virtuality” [Карасик 2003: 18;
- ✓ concepts that are actively used in society.

J. N. Maslova proposed a structural typology of concepts [Маслова 2014: 54]:

- ✓ the information units stored in our minds are of a linguistic and nonlinear nature;
- ✓ they differ in complexity.

The cognitive structures that form the conceptsphere of the literal text, the so-called “extremely deep semantics”, define the expression of content and character, aimed at understanding the mechanisms of combining the categories of linguistic semantics with the general cognitive categories formed by the perception of the universe through human thought [see: Бабич 2006: 43].

Thus, the main and cultural types of literal concepts are relevant for the cognitive compilation and modeling of the conceptsphere of an literal text, which can be interpreted in the work as diminishing concepts, developing concepts.

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